

14. Agroforestry in the CAP post 1/1/2023

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EURAF is an NGO, established in Paris on 16/11/2012, with a French Registration number of [W343014937](#), and a Transparency Register ID of [913270437706-82](#)). It aims “to promote the adoption of agroforestry practices across Europe by supporting efforts to develop awareness, education, research, policy making and investments which foster the use of trees on farms”. It has a network of 31 affiliated entities in 23 countries.

Agroforestry is mentioned in nine sections of the Strategic Plan Regulation. EURAF welcomes these mentions and especially Article 4 which makes clear that agroforestry is an integral part of agricultural land. It remains to be seen how Member States will interpret the GAEC-8 rules in relation to tree-landscape-features, and the agroforestry options in Ecoschemes (Pillar I). Agroforestry is also recommended for inclusion in the Pillar II Agri-Environment-Climate Measures and Investment Measures (Pillar II).

On the 6th December the three Regulations defining the new CAP were signed into law. Two of these mention agroforestry, and the relevant sections are listed below.

1. The Strategic Plan Regulation ([2021/2115](#))

This mentions agroforestry in nine sections, quoted below

- **Recital 14.** The framework definitions of ‘agricultural area’ **should ensure that Member States cover agroforestry systems**, where trees are grown in agricultural parcels on which agricultural activities are carried out to improve the sustainable use of the land.
- **Recital 26** The Union needs to improve the response to societal demands on food and health, including high-quality, safe, and nutritious food produced in a sustainable way. In order to advance in that direction, specific sustainable farming practices, such as organic farming, integrated pest management, agro-ecology, **agroforestry** or precision farming, will need to be promoted. Similarly, actions to promote higher levels of animal welfare and initiatives to combat antimicrobial resistance should also be stimulated.
- **Recital 72** Support for management commitments could also include payments for other types of intervention supporting environmentally friendly production systems such as agro-ecology, conservation agriculture and integrated production; forest environmental and climate services and forest conservation; **premiums for forests and establishment of agroforestry systems**; animal welfare; conservation, sustainable use and development of genetic resources, in particular through traditional breeding methods. Member States should be allowed to develop other schemes under that type of intervention on the basis of their needs. That type of payment should cover additional costs and income foregone only resulting from commitments going beyond the baseline of mandatory standards and requirements established in Union and national law, as well as conditionality, as laid down in the CAP Strategic Plan. It should be possible for commitments related to that type of intervention to be undertaken for a pre-established annual or pluri-annual period and go beyond seven years where duly justified.
- **Recital 73** Forestry interventions should contribute to the implementation of Commission communication of 16 July 2021, entitled ‘New EU Forest Strategy for 2030’ and, where appropriate, to **widening the use of agroforestry systems**. Interventions should be based on sustainable forest management plans or equivalent instruments that duly consider effective carbon storage and sequestration from the atmosphere while enhancing biodiversity protection and may comprise forest area development and sustainable management of forests, including the afforestation of land, fire prevention and the **creation and regeneration of agroforestry systems**; ...
- **Article 4 Para 3** ‘Agricultural area’ shall be determined in such a way as to comprise arable land, permanent crops and permanent grassland, **including when they form agroforestry systems on that area**. It is further clarified in the [Implementing Regulation](#) that “information shall be provided on elements of agroforestry systems when it is established or maintained on the agricultural area, specifying these elements for each type of agricultural area (arable land, permanent crops and permanent grassland)”.
- **Article 15 Para 3** - Through the farm advisory services, appropriate assistance shall be offered along the cycle of the farm development, including for the setting-up for the first time, conversion of production patterns towards consumer demand, innovative practises, agricultural techniques for resilience to climate

change, including **agroforestry** and agroecology, improved animal welfare, and where necessary safety standards and social support.

- **Article 70 Para 2a** - Member States shall provide payments only for commitments which: (b) go beyond the relevant minimum requirements for the use of fertiliser and plant protection products or for animal welfare, as well as other relevant mandatory requirements established by national and Union law; that requirement does not apply to commitments related to **agroforestry systems** and the maintenance of afforested areas;
- **Result Indicator 17**. Afforested land: Area supported for afforestation, **agroforestry** and restoration, including breakdowns (also included as one of the core set of indicators which must be reported on annually pursuant to Article 142)¹
- **Output Indicator.16** Number of hectares or number of other units under maintenance commitments for afforestation and agroforestry

There are also mentions of shrubs and trees in the following sections:

- **Article 4 Para 3 (c)**. - ‘permanent grassland and permanent pasture’ (together referred to as ‘permanent grassland’) shall be land that is used to grow grasses or other herbaceous forage naturally (self-seeded) or through cultivation (sown) and that has not been included in the crop rotation of the holding for five years or more and, where Member States so decide, that has not been ploughed up, or tilled, or reseeded with different types of grass or other herbaceous forage, for five years or more. **It may include other species, such as shrubs or trees, which can be grazed and, where Member States so decide, other species such as shrubs or trees which produce animal feed, provided that the grasses and other herbaceous forage remain predominant.**
- **Result indicator 34**. Preserving landscape features: Share of utilised agricultural area (UAA) under supported commitments for managing landscape features, **including hedgerows and trees**. This is also a core indicator for annual reporting.

Rules for “Conditionality” are defined in [Annex 3 of Regulation 2021/2115](#), with 9 “Good Agricultural and Environmental Practices (GAEC) and 11 Statutory Management Requirements. Most of the GAECs can be contributed to by trees on agricultural land, but the rules for GAEC8 (minimum share of agricultural area devoted to non-productive areas or features) - are particularly relevant **since these “non-productive features” (sic) include productive trees and hedges**². There are three options available to farmers:

- A. Minimum share of at least 4 % of arable land at farm level devoted to non-productive areas and features, including land lying fallow.
- B. Where a farmer commits to devote at least 7 % of his/her arable land to non-productive areas or features, including land lying fallow, under an enhanced eco-scheme in accordance with Article 31(6), the share to be attributed to compliance with this GAEC standard shall be limited to 3 %.
- C. Minimum share of at least 7 % of arable land at farm level if this includes also catch crops or nitrogen fixing crops, cultivated without the use of plant protection products, of which 3 % shall be land lying fallow or non-productive features. Member States should use the weighting factor of 0,3 for catch crops.

2. Regulation on Financing, Management and Monitoring of the CAP. ([2021/2116](#)) (the “Horizontal Regulation”)

- **Article 25 1 (b)** “Ensure agri-economic and agri-environmental-climate monitoring of agricultural land use and agricultural land use change, **including agro-forestry**, and monitoring of the condition of soil, crops, agricultural landscapes and agricultural land so as to enable estimates to be made, in particular as regards yields and agricultural production and agricultural impacts associated with exceptional circumstances, and to enable the assessment of the resilience of agricultural systems and progress towards the achievement of the relevant United Nations Sustainable Development Goals.”

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¹ For the 3 climate, environment and biodiversity objectives Core Indicators are I10, R14, R17 (climate); O34, I15, I16, I18, R19, R20, R21, R22, R24 (environment); and C33, I21, R29, R34 (biodiversity). See the Indicators [Implementing Regulation](#)

² The main [Implementing Regulation](#) specifies the MS should use the following indicative list: land lying fallow, hedgerows, individual or groups of trees, trees rows, field margins, patches, buffer strips, ditches, streams, small ponds, small wetlands, stonewalls, cairns, terraces, cultural features, other.